

Analyzing transition process of technological space based on graph convolutional network

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Abstract

Recently, understanding the technology transition becomes more important for pursuing the effective detection on R&D trend and further achieving technology innovation. This paper attempts to analyze the specific structure of technology transition by jointly applying Markov Chain and Graph Convolutional Network to the entire EPO citations of 889,700 triadic patents at the level of IPC. Findings of this research could provide the node classification and link prediction in terms of technological transitions. It is expected that the methodology and result of this paper could be utilized for R&D management and related policy implications.

Introduction

Recently, technological innovation has been considered important to achieve technological competitiveness. An important aspect is that the technological innovation could be effectively accelerated by the technological convergence, which leads to the creation of a new field and brings the technological competitiveness (Lee et al., 2015). In this context, technological convergence represents the transition process of convergence or fusion of existing technologies (Karvonen and Kassi, 2012). Then, it is necessary to focus on the technological transition to other technologies as one of the ways to effectively reveal the mechanism of technological convergence. In this paper, we focus on the technology transition structure in order to effectively know and exploit technology convergence.

Unfortunately, despite its increasing importance, there have been insufficient attempts to study technology transition. This paper analyzes the transition structure of technology convergence with emphasis on emerging areas. Markov chain is used to model the transition process of technological convergence, and graph convolutional network is successively applied to predict the emerging convergence. The triadic patent family database provided by the OECD is effectively used for the analysis (Baudery and Dumont, 2006; OECD, 2021). It is expected that the entire TPF data across different domains could effectively lead us to investigate the process of technology convergence (Karvonen and Kassi, 2012).

The results of this research could contribute to R&D management and related policy making. The Markov chain with GCN-based methodology is also expected to provide a better understanding of the transition process for tracking technology convergence. This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the previous research on technology transitions, and the research problem is provided. Section 3 illustrates a research framework, followed by sections 4 and 5, which propose the current research in progress, its implications and research contributions.

Literature review and research issues

Technology transitions for technological convergence

Technologies are continuously changing to meet the demands from different sectors (Safarzynska, 2012). In particular, the Schumpeterian perspective suggests that technological change and further progress could promote further economic development (Mulder, 2001). As Meyer-Krahmer and Schmoch (1998) suggested, technological change could have the path dependency and technological lock-in to the emerging technologies. In addition, Safarzynska and Bergh (2011) modeled these technological changes to capture the technological development. Lee and Sohn (2018) analyzed how the technological factors are related to the technological evolution, focusing on the convergence process. In this context, the technological change needs to be studied and managed through the active transitions between technologies. Then, the creative destruction could occur with different technologies for the pursuit of technological progress.

Specifically, the technological convergence has the convergence process of two or more different technologies to create new areas of technology (Curran and Leker, 2011). It shows that there is the transition process for convergences, and this process could lead to the promising areas (Martin et al., 2012). In addition, the neo-Schumpeterian perspective further explains that the transition process for technological convergences could provide the new competitiveness for industries and governments (Allarakhia and Walsh, 2012). Apparently, the technological convergence is understood as the trigger to facilitate the exchange of technologies across industries (Karvonen and Kassi, 2012). More importantly, technological convergence could be the result of technological transitions. Therefore, this paper focuses on understanding and exploiting the technological transitions.

Data and methodology

Patent citations analysis for technology transitions

Technological transitions to study technological convergence could be achieved from several perspectives. One of the effective ways is based on patent analysis (Karvonen and Kassi, 2012). Patent analysis has provided some technological insights and useful indicators of technological evolution (Sen and Sharma, 2006). Therefore, a more systematic analysis on a specific domain is expected based on patent analysis. For example, Curran and Leker (2011) approached technological convergence by using the co-classification of patents. In this regard, Karvonen and Kassi (2012) suggested that the analysis of large patents could properly reveal the understanding of technological convergence.

Patents could well represent the quantitative aspect of technologies and their different characteristics. For example, patent claims explain the legal rights of technologies. The International Patent Classification (IPC) even provides the detailed information on technological domains. The patent citations could provide the systematic understanding of the interactions and transitions between different technologies (Allarakhia and Walsh, 2012). Recently, graph mining on the patent citations has been widely attempted to discover the complicated interactions in technological evolution (Biju and Soumyo, 2001; He and Fallah, 2009; Gress, 2010).

Methodology

In the current paper, the citations among different patents are considered as a process of technological transition. Such a process can be effectively modeled with a Markov chain. Zunde and Slamecka (1971) attempted to model scientific development using citations of social science articles. Through the Markov chain, they showed the tendency of shifting concentration from science and technology to social science areas. Geller (1978) showed the relationship between the influence measure based on citations and the application of Markov chain theory. Pao and McCreery (1986) explained the application of Markov chain to different domains. They also illustrated the methodology and provided the useful applications using Markov chain. Hingley and Bas (2009) applied Markov Chain to EPO applications to study the transition between applicant groups characterized by the number of applications.

Markov chain is a mathematical system that experiences transitions from one state to another state, among a finite or countable number of possible states. A Markov chain assumes that the next state depends only on the current state.

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(X_{t+1} = x_{t+1} | X_1 = x_1, X_2 = x_2, \dots, X_t = x_t) \\ = \Pr(X_{t+1} = x_{t+1} | X_t = x_t) \end{aligned}$$

Formula 1. Markov Chain

Discrete Time Markov chain continuously moves from one state to another state, and the probability p_{ij} of moving among states in n steps is considered as transition.

$$p_{ij}^{(n)} = \Pr(X_n = s_j | X_0 = s_i)$$

Formula 2. Transition Probability

This paper is based on Markov chain, which studies the transitions of emerging technologies. As a result of applying Markov chain to the technology transitions, the state transition matrix is obtained, and this matrix could provide the detailed information of technological convergence. This matrix indicates the transitions from one technology area to another technology area with probability. Thus, the transition represents that two different specific areas are connected as the convergence.

Based on such a matrix that shows the adjacency relationships between technologies, Graph Convolutional Network (hereafter GCN, Zhang et al., 2019) is sequentially applied to this transition matrix to predict the transitions and technology areas. GCN has been widely used to explain graph-based problems, such as node classification, recommendation, and link prediction. In particular, GCN employs the layer-wise graph convolution for obtaining the node embeddings on a given graph. The node embeddings are measured from the node and its neighbors.

Analysis

First, the total EPO citations of triadic patents are regrouped to the 7-digit IPC level, which indicates the specific technological domains defined by WIPO, in order to examine the transitions between technological domains. Then, the citation matrix is constructed with the column of citing IPCs, the row of cited IPCs, and the element of citation frequency among IPCs as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Patent Citation matrix at IPC level

In order to find more meaningful relationships among IPCs, such a frequency-based matrix is scaled into the similarity matrix among IPCs. Markov chain is then applied to the similarity matrix to track the structure of technology transition. Jaccard similarity is applied to patent citations as a measure of similarity in Formula 1. The similarity normalizes the whole citation matrix, which has the large frequency and different scales by IPCs.

$$J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}$$

Formula 3. Jaccard Similarity

The given similarity matrix is considered as the transition matrix of the Markov chain, and each row of the similarity matrix is normalized by its corresponding row. Based on the similarity matrix between IPCs, the Markov chain is constructed. Markov Chain has been applied to many processes and statistical models, and it is expected to fit well to model the technological transitions. In this paper, the IPCs are considered as random variables of the technology state by assuming the citation process as a time-homogeneous discrete-time Markov chain. The resulting stationary Markov matrix is obtained to indicate the transition probability between IPCs. It is further represented as a graph to discover the important IPC of technology transition as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Graph of Markov Chain with Sub-group detection

Finally, GCN is deployed to the graph, representing the steady probability of technology transitions in Markov chain. Under the assumption that the absorbing state in the Markov chain representing the technological transition is the important basis of potential technological convergence, it is classified whether each node is an absorbing state in terms of GCN-based node classification. Absorbing states were considered as promising domains where technological convergence is expected to occur by having most of the technology transitions. In addition, for the prediction of technological convergence in the process of technology transition, link prediction, which predicts the technology transition from the above absorbing technology, was performed using the steady probability matrix of the technological transition in Markov chain. Through this process, it is expected to propose a methodology for predicting technological convergences based on technological transitions in Markov chain.

Specifically, the proposed methodology is empirically applied to ESG areas. It is expected to contribute to the planning and execution of practical R&D by predicting what kind of technology transition process the technologies in the ESG field represented by IPC head toward, which technologies are in the absorbing state, and predicting the future technology convergence represented by the edge based on this.

Conclusion

This paper focused on the transitions of emerging technologies for deeply understanding the technological convergences based on triadic patents. Markov Chain was first applied to the entire citations between IPCs, and the resulting transition matrix was, then, measured by Jaccard similarity. GCN is conducted on that transition matrix for classifying nodes and predicting links. The proposed methodology is one of the first efforts to exploit Markov Chain and GCN for identifying the technology transitions. Findings of this research are expected to contribute to the acceleration of technological convergences.

References

- Allarakhia, M., Walsh, S., (2012). Analyzing and organizing nanotechnology development: Application of the institutional analysis development framework to nanotechnology consortia. *Technovation*, 32, 216-226.
- Baudery, M., Dumont, B., (2006). Comparing firms' triadic patent applications across countries: Is there a gap in terms of R&D effort or a gap in terms of performances? *Research Policy*, 35, 324-342.
- Biju, P. A., Soumyo, D. M., (2001). Innovation assessment through patent analysis. *Technovation*, 21, 245-252.
- Curran C. S., Leker, J., (2011). Patent indicators for monitoring convergence – examples from NFF and ICT. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 78, 256-273.
- Geller, N. L. (1978). On the citation influence methodology of Pinski and Narin. *Information Processing & Management*, 14(2), 93-95.
- Gress, B., (2010). Properties of the USPTO patent citation network: 1963-2002. *World Patent Information*, 32, 3-21.
- He, J., Fallah, M. H., (2009). Is inventor network structure a predictor of cluster evolution? *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 76, 91-106.
- Hingley, P., & Bas, S. (2009). Numbers and sizes of applicants at the European Patent Office. *World Patent Information*, 31(4), 285-298.
- Karvonen, M., Kässi, T., (2013). Patent citations as a tool for analysing the early stages of convergence. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 80(6), 1094-1107.
- Lee, W. S., Han, E. J., & Sohn, S. Y. (2015). Predicting the pattern of technology convergence using big-data technology on large-scale triadic patents. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 100, 317-329.

- Lee, W. S., & Sohn, S. Y. (2018). Effects of standardization on the evolution of information and communications technology. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 132, 308-317.
- Meyer-Krahmer, F., & Schmoch, U. (1998). Science-based technologies: university–industry interactions in four fields. *Research policy*, 27(8), 835-851.
- Mulder, P., De Groot, H. L. F., Hofkes, M. W., (2001). Economic growth and technological change: A comparison of insights from a neo-classical and an evolutionary perspective. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 68, 151-171.
- OECD (2021). OECD Triadic Patent Families database.
- Pinski, G., & Narin, F. (1976). Citation influence for journal aggregates of scientific publications: Theory, with application to the literature of physics. *Information Processing & Management*, 12(5), 297-312.
- Safarzyńska, K., van den Bergh, J. C.J.M., (2011). Beyond replicator dynamics: Innovation-selection dynamics and optimal diversity. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 78, 229-245.
- Safarzyńska, K., Frenken, K., van den Bergh, J. C.J.M., (2012). Evolutionary theorizing and modeling of sustainability transitions. *Research Policy*, 41, 1011-1024.
- Sen, S. K., Sharma, H. P., (2006). A note on growth of superconductivity patents with two new indicators. *Information Processing and Management*, 42, 1643-1651.
- Zhang, S., Tong, H., Xu, J., & Maciejewski, R. (2019). Graph convolutional networks: a comprehensive review. *Computational Social Networks*, 6(1), 1-23.
- Zunde, P., & Slamecka, V. (1971). Predictive models of scientific progress. *Information Storage and Retrieval*, 7(3), 103-109.